

BASIC NOTIONS IN ELT CURRICULUM DESIGN AND DEVELOPMENT

Manuel Jiménez Raya
Universidad de Granada

Any rigorous and socially worthwhile education must not only reflect the complexity of studying the world around us but must also be developed in concordance with an exciting vision of schooling. Such a vision respects the untapped capacities of human beings and the role that education can play in producing a just, inclusive, democratic, and imaginative future. (Kincheloe, 2003: 111)

In this paper we explore some of the central concepts in the study of curriculum and look at a number of different models which have been developed to specify and assist in the planning, presentation and evaluation of learning.

1. INTRODUCTION

The organization of schooling has long been associated with the idea of a curriculum. In this chapter, we explore curriculum theory and practice and its relation to modern language teaching.

The idea of curriculum is not new at all - but the way it has been understood at different moments has changed over the years - and there remains considerable dispute as to what it actually means. The word curriculum has its origin in the running/chariot tracks of ancient Greece. Literally, it was *a course*. In Latin, *currere* was to run. Nowadays curriculum is often taken to mean a course of study. When we set our imaginations free from the narrow notion that a course of study is a series of textbooks or specific outline of topics to be covered and objectives to be attained, broader more meaningful notions emerge. A curriculum can become one's life course of action. It can mean the paths we have followed and the paths we intend to follow (Connelly & Clandinin, 1988).

A useful starting point for us here is the definition provided by Kerr and taken up by Kelly in his work on the subject. Kerr defines curriculum as

All the learning which is planned and guided by the school, whether it is carried on in groups or individually, inside or outside the school. (quoted in Kelly 1983: 10).

From this definition we can highlight two basic features:

- **Learning in school is a planned and guided activity.** In a curriculum, teachers typically specify in advance what they intend to achieve and what they are going to do to guarantee its attainment.
- **The definition of curriculum refers to formal education/schooling.** We should recognize that our current appreciation of curriculum theory and practice emerged in the school and in relation to other schooling ideas such as *subject* and *lesson*.

In general, curriculum planning can be regarded as the methodical attempt by those involved in teaching (education experts, methodologists, and teachers) to determine and plan systematically the educational enterprise. Curriculum decisions not only involve questions about how learners learn, but also what learning is appropriate and when it is best learned. In addition, the way learning is assessed directly influences what is taught and when it is expected to be learned. Language teaching experts believe that curriculum and assessment should be planned based on the best knowledge of theory and research about how people learn a second language, with attention given to individual learners' needs and interests in relation to programme goals.

In this unit, we will explore some of the central concepts underlying the study of the curriculum and look at a number of different models which have been developed to specify and assist in the planning, presentation and evaluation of teaching and learning.

2. APPROACHES TO CURRICULUM

A curriculum is an organized framework that delineates the content learners are to learn, the processes through which learners attain the identified curricular goals, what teachers do to help children achieve these goals, and the context in which teaching and learning occur. The concept of curriculum encompasses prevailing theories, approaches, and models, hence, the different conceptualizations of the term. Curriculum theory is not understood equally by educationalists, teachers, and curriculum theorists. A curriculum is a plan of what one intends to achieve through teaching. This plan typically reflects the author's views on education. Views on the education process differ considerably. In fact, curriculum development is a profoundly value-laden activity and is never value-free (Klein, 1990). The curriculum can be looked at as attempt to identify teacher and learner activity in the classroom, to describe what actually does happen, and to attempt to reconcile the differences between what "should be" and what actually "is" (Nunan, 1988a:10).

Traditionally, several trends have been identified in curriculum theory:

- Curriculum as a body of knowledge (syllabus) to be transmitted in school
- Curriculum as the achievement of pre-established aims (product) (Tyler, 1949; Taba, 1962)
- Curriculum as process (Stenhouse, 1975)
- Curriculum as praxis (Grundy, 1987)

2.1 Curriculum as a syllabus to be transmitted

Some curriculum traditions do not distinguish syllabus design from curriculum development. Nunan (1988b) mentions that it is possible to distinguish in the relevant literature a broad and a narrow approach to syllabus design. The narrow approach draws a marked distinction between the specification of syllabus design and methodology. Syllabus design is regarded as being concerned essentially with the selection and grading of language content, while methodology is concerned with *the study of the practices and procedures used in teaching, and the principles that underlie them* (Richards, Platt and Weber, 1985: 117). In other words, the syllabus is concerned with the *what* of teaching whereas methodology is about the *how*.

Those who adopt a broader perspective question this strict separation, arguing that with the development of communicative language teaching the division between content and tasks is difficult to sustain. In some instances as Curzon (1985) indicates,

syllabus designers usually follow the traditional textbook approach of a 'sequence of contents', or a pattern prescribed by a 'logical' approach to the subject. Thus, an approach to curriculum theory and practice which focuses on syllabus is only really concerned with content or the body of knowledge to be transmitted. In this sense, curriculum is a body of knowledge-content and/or subjects. This paradigm regards education as the process by which these are transmitted or delivered to students by the most effective methods that can be devised (Blenkin et al., 1992: 23).

2.2 The product approach to curriculum design

The product approach to curriculum design starts out by trying to define the kind of output or product that will result after the teaching process. This approach derives from industry and commerce and sees education as a technical exercise. If we were to manufacture a computer, for example, we would first identify the needs of potential buyers, make plans, implement the plans, and then we would evaluate whether the final product actually matches the initial objectives. This product focus is also found in education. From this perspective, a curriculum is just one way of organising the work of modern language teachers. A product curriculum is said to involve working on rather than with people. The focus entails the teaching of skills and attributes that experts hold to be desirable.

Tyler, one of the most influential curriculum theorists in the XX century, provides a model for the systematic development of the curriculum. For Tyler (1949: 1), the development of any curriculum for any subject whatsoever must be based on a consideration of four fundamental questions:

- What educational purposes should the school seek to attain?
- What educational experiences can be provided that are likely to attain these purposes?
- How can these educational experiences be effectively organised?
- How can we evaluate whether these purposes are being achieved?

Question number one focuses the curriculum designer on the nature of the educational enterprise in which s/he is involved. This question requires the determination of goals and objectives. Question number 2 is related to the need to specify the content of instruction that will be used to attain the aims and objectives. The third question points out the need to articulate the methodological principles that will be used as a guide for teaching. The last question is connected with the need to specify how the teacher will determine whether the aims and objectives have been attained. In this approach, objectives are set, a plan is drawn up, then implemented, and the outcomes are measured. The table below shows the steps involved in the development of a product curriculum:

Planning the product curriculum

Step 1: Needs analysis

Step 2: Formulation of objectives

Step 3: Selection of content

Step 4: Organization of content

Step 5: Selection of learning experiences

Step 6: Organization of learning experiences

Step 7: Determination of what to evaluate, the procedures (ways) and the instruments for evaluation.

(Taba,1962)

This approach to curriculum design is attractive because it presents a systematic approach to curriculum theory and practice. In fact, some countries have attempted to make the student experience 'teacher proof'. To this end, the curriculum programme is designed outside the school and the teacher is expected to implement it, in turn, teachers themselves are evaluated on the basis of the products of their actions. This curriculum is said to turn teachers into technicians. Among the characteristics of this approach we can mention:

- Objectives are formulated in behavioural terms. These typically provide a clear description of the outcome. This facilitates the selection of content and the organization of educational experiences, as well as the evaluation of the outcomes of learning. As a consequence, this model is highly concerned with measurability. The idea inherited from Behaviourism is that behaviour can be objectively measured. Critics, however, point out the existence of certain dangers here - there always has to be some uncertainty about what is being measured. They also point out that it is often very difficult to measure what the impact of particular experiences has been. In addition, in order to teach effectively and to be able to measure knowledge and skills, they have to be broken down into smaller and smaller units. This can lead to a focus of this approach to curriculum theory and practice on the parts rather than the whole; on the trivial, rather than the significant. Critics argue that this decomposition often leads to long lists of skills or competencies, resembling a shopping list.
- The programme (syllabus) occupies a central position in this curriculum model. 'A programme of activities (by teachers and pupils) is designed so that pupils will attain so far as possible certain educational and other schooling ends or objectives' (Grundy 1987: 11). Critics point out that the problem is that the programme exists prior and independently of the learning experience. Learners have little to say. In fact, they are told what to learn and how to learn it. Furthermore, the success of such programmes is determined on the basis of whether pre-specified behavioural objectives are attained. Classroom interaction is also typically inhibited in those cases in which the plan is tightly adhered to.

- The subject matter is organised in form of disciplines in outcomes and processes of curriculum development.
- Outcomes deal primarily with predetermined and logically organized skills or bodies of knowledge that all students are to learn.
- There is also a focus on the development of students' intellectual capacities
- It represents a linear view of the teaching-learning process. In the first instance aims and objectives are specified, content is then organised, and finally, after the teaching has been completed, there is an evaluation phase to determine whether the aims and objectives have been achieved.
- The curriculum, essentially, is a set of documents for implementation.

In addition to some of the criticisms mentioned above, another important objection to the product curriculum is that it embodies an end-means view of education. Lawton (1973), one of the most vocal critics, maintains that this model based on the four-stage, sequential progression from objectives to content selection to methodology and finally to evaluation is far too simple. Criticisms to the linear model led Wheeler (1967) to suggest a cyclical model because it would make much more sense since information collected in the evaluation could feed back into the process, thus leading to a more integrated model.

According to Smith (1996, 2000), one way of viewing this is that teachers simply get it wrong - they ought to work with objectives. In his opinion, this problem needs serious consideration. It should not be dismissed in this way. Further, the difficulties that educators experience with objectives in the classroom may point to something inherently wrong with the approach - that it is not grounded in the study of educational exchanges. It is a model of curriculum theory and practice basically imported from technological and industrial settings.

“One objection to the whole curriculum model based on the four-stage progression from objectives to content to organisations to evaluation is that this is far too simple. For one reason, it is open to Bruner’s suggestion that leaving evaluation until the final stage of the curriculum process is rather like doing military intelligence after the war is over: in other words, evaluation should take place at every stage. This would make the curriculum model a cyclical one rather than a linear model.”

2.3 The process approach to curriculum design

Some theorists dissatisfied with the previous models have pointed out some other problems. One of these is related to the mismatch between what a curriculum states and what actually happens in the classroom, that is, the difference between the planned and the implemented curriculum. Much of the research concerning teacher thinking and classroom interaction, and curriculum innovation has pointed to the lack of impact on actual pedagogic practice of technological models (Stenhouse, 1974; Cornbleth, 1990). This paradigm looks at curriculum theory and practice via process. In this sense curriculum is not a physical thing, but rather the interaction of teachers, students and knowledge. To put it differently, curriculum is what actually happens in the classroom and what people do to prepare and evaluate. The most outstanding feature in this

model the constant interaction of the different elements involved. Stenhouse defines tentatively the curriculum as *an attempt to communicate the essential principles and features of an educational proposal in such a form that it is open to critical scrutiny and capable of effective translation into practice.* (1975:4).

He suggests that a curriculum should minimally consist of three major parts relating to planning, empirical study and justification. Each of these consists of subsidiary parts as set out in the following table:

A. Planning consists of:

- 1 Principles for the selection of content - what is to be learned and taught.
- 2 Principles for the development of a teaching strategy - how it is to be learned and taught.
- 3 Principles for the making of decisions about sequence.
- 4 Principles on which to diagnose the strengths and weakness of individual students and differentiate the general principles 1, 2 and 3 above to meet individual cases.

B. In empirical study:

- 1 Principles on which to study and evaluate the progress of the students.
- 2 Principles on which to study and evaluate the progress of teachers.
- 3 Guidance as to the feasibility of implementing the curriculum in varying school contexts, pupil contexts, environments and peer group situations.
- 4 Information about the variability of effects in differing contexts and on different pupils and an understanding of the causes of variation.

C. In relation to justification:

A formulation of the aim or intention of the curriculum which is accessible to critical scrutiny.

(Stenhouse, 1975: 5)

In language teaching, Widdowson (1979) criticises curriculum programmes based on the product approach as follows:

...inventories of language functions and notions do not necessarily reflect the way languages are learned any more than do inventories of grammatical points and lexical items. He also claims that dividing language into discrete units of whatever type misrepresents the nature of language as communication.

van Lier (1996) also understands the term curriculum in a *holistic* and *process* sense. He understands that in a process-oriented curriculum the pedagogical interaction is motivated by the designer's understanding of learning rather than by a list of desired products. For van Lier (1996), a curriculum should be holistic in the sense that all its

elements and actions should be motivated by and understood in relation to all other parts and actions in an integrative way. In a process curriculum, the determination of goals and objectives and the evaluation of their attainment are an intrinsic part of the curriculum process. They are not regarded as pre-established constraints that are imposed on it from outsiders. In this context, *outsider* is understood as the person not directly involved in the teaching and implementation of the curriculum. He adds that Any curriculum must be based on our knowledge of the learning process and the learning context, as well as on our values and purposes (including those of the teacher, student, parent, and any other stakeholder). The key to responsible (and effective) pedagogical interaction is understanding the learner (which includes understanding learning), and a theory of learning is therefore needed to underpin the development of strategies for pedagogical interaction.

The basic features of the process model developed by Stenhouse (1975) are:

- It assigns a central place in the curriculum process to an analysis of what is actually happening in the classroom, in contrast to the statements that are often made about what ought to be happening.
- It is thus centred on the implemented rather than the planned curriculum.
- It recognises the central role played by the teacher in the curriculum development process.
- It gives recognition to the fact that effective curriculum development is largely a matter of effective teacher development by suggesting that curriculum change will only find its way into the classroom if teachers themselves become the principal agents of curriculum change through critical analysis and reflection on their current performance. In fact, its successful implementation is dependent upon the quality of teachers. The approach is dependent upon the cultivation of wisdom and meaning-making in the classroom (Smith, 2002). One of the dangers of the process model is that teachers sometimes reduce the process to a number of skills. This way when they are able to demonstrate certain skills, they are deemed to have completed the process. Therefore, the actions have become the ends; the processes have become the product. Whether or not students are able to apply the skills to make sense of the world around them is somehow overlooked (Grundy 1987: 77).
- The process curriculum consists of *exploring, articulating, examining, and developing the constraints and resources in the educational setting, from the perspective of clear principles which guide the search, or rather, the research* (van Lier, 1996: 8).

2.4 Curriculum as praxis

This model is a development of the process curriculum discussed above. The difference lies in the fact that the interpretation of curriculum as praxis on top of placing a special emphasis on judgement and meaning making, as the process model, it also makes explicit statements about the interests it serves. Grundy (1987) draws Habermas and Freire together in order to make an explicit commitment to emancipation. From this perspective, action is not merely informed, it is also committed. It is praxis. Praxis is not simply action based on reflection. It refers to action which embodies certain qualities.

These comprise a commitment to human well being and the search for truth, and respect for others. It is the action of people who are free, who are able to act for themselves. Moreover, *praxis* is always risky. It requires that a person 'makes a wise and prudent practical judgement about how to act in *this* situation' (Carr and Kemmis 1986: 190). This praxis combines reflection with action in the social realm. Within praxis, meaning is viewed as a social construction, and the ultimate goal of the critique is social transformation. In this sense, the curriculum is a matter of negotiation between teacher and learner. Grundy (1987) offers teacher action research as a form of praxis; embodying reflection, action and change.

In the United States, curriculum theory has developed from the critical theory of the early Frankfurt school to researchers who now try to become actively engaged in promoting social change within the education system and the culture itself. Besides they seek to promote change by "becoming part of the self-consciousness of oppressed social groups (Hoy and McCarthy, 1994)". These researchers have rejected the realism of the past to embrace theories from postmodernism.

Building again on the work of Habermas, Grundy describes critical pedagogy as one which confronts reality, actively incorporates Freire's conscientization (developing consciousness, but consciousness that is understood to have the power to transform), challenges ideological distortion and incorporates action as a fundamental part of knowing.

Critical pedagogy places the learning experience beyond that of the learner; it is usually regarded as a process that identifies the experiences of both teacher and learner as problematic.

[It] allows, indeed encourages, students and teachers together to confront the real problems of their existence and relationships... When students confront the real problems of their existence they will soon also be faced with their own oppression (Grundy 1987: 105).

STOP AND THINK

DISCUSSION

- a) What is a curriculum?
 - b) What are the four fundamental questions in curriculum design?
 - c) What are the main trends in curriculum theory and development?
 - d) What are the basic characteristics of a product-focused curriculum?
 - e) What are the steps in planning the product curriculum?
 - f) What does curriculum planning consists of according to Stenhouse?
 - g) What are the main criticisms of the product approach to curriculum design?
 - h) What is the difference between the notions of curriculum as process and as praxis?
 - i) What are the main features of the process approach to curriculum design?
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3. CURRICULUM ELEMENTS

Curriculum theory encompasses philosophy and value systems; the main components of the curriculum are: purposes, content, methodology and evaluation, and the processes whereby curricula are developed, implemented and evaluated.

3.1 Goals, aims and objectives

TASK

Search the web for information on Bloom's taxonomy of educational objectives. Prepare a summary and draw implications for TEFL.

Goals are very general and broad. Aims are more specific, and are long-term - the target to be aimed at. Conventionally, objectives are the short- to medium-term goals. Both are generally regarded as important because, without general aims to provide direction, it is possible to become lost in the attempt to satisfy a range of short term objectives.

By **objectives**, Widdowson (1983) means "the pedagogic intentions of a particular course of study to be achieved within the period of that course and in principle measurable by some assessment device at the end of the course". By **aims** he means "the purposes to which learning will be put after the end of the course" (Widdowson, 1983:6-7).

STOP AND THINK

Suggest a goal which could cover these three learning purposes:

- ◆ to communicate socially with members of the target community
- ◆ to develop the survival skills necessary to communicate in the FL
- ◆ to establish and maintain social relationships

Educational objectives provide the basis for building curricula and the tests for measuring the understanding of those curricula by students. To these examiners, a classification system represented the appropriate place to start. In any curriculum design, certain ends will have to be reached through the specification of content and methodology. In the 1950's objectives were classified under three domains: the *cognitive*, which is concerned with the intellectual abilities and operations; the *affective*, which is the domain of attitudes, values and appreciation; and the *psychomotor*, the area of motor skills, important in technical contexts. The latter are also relevant in the acquisition of pronunciation in a FL.

STOP AND THINK

Tyler suggested that there were four ways of stating objectives:

1. Specify the things that the teacher or instructor is to do
 2. Specify course content (topics, concepts, generalizations, etc.)
 3. Specify generalized patterns of behaviour (e.g. "to develop critical thinking")
 4. Specify the kinds of behaviour which learners will be able to exhibit after instruction
- ◆ Which of these ways of stating objectives do you think is likely to be most useful? Why?
 - ◆ What criticisms, if any, would you make of the other methods?
 - ◆ Can you think of any other methods of stating objectives?

Mager (1975) identifies three components in an objective:

- 1 *Behaviour*. First, the terminal behaviour is identified by name; you can specify the kind of behaviour that will be accepted as evidence that the learner has achieved the objective. This is usually done by using an action verb that describes the outcomes of teaching as student performance.
- 2 *Conditions*. Second, the desired behaviour is defined further by describing the conditions under which the behaviour will be expected to occur.
- 3 *Standards*. Third, the criteria of acceptable performance are specified by describing how well the learner must perform to be considered acceptable. In other words, a criterion for success is established.

Following the conventional prescription for behavioural objectives, Steiner proposes that a performance objective should state:

- 1 What the students will do (e.g narrate a story).
- 2 Under what conditions (e.g. in class without prior preparation)
- 3 Within what time (e.g. 10 minutes,...)
- 4 To what level of mastery (e.g fluently)

Steiner further gives three main criteria for terminal course objectives. First of all, terminal course objectives must provide clear **guidance** to the prospective users and as the specificity increases through the refinement process, greater clarity should

appear. Secondly, the terminal course objective should be **relevant** by being meaningful to the learner, related to the educational goal from which it is derived and desirable in terms of the present and future expectations of the school and its related groups. Finally, such an objective should be **feasible** if there is a good probability of its being achieved.

STOP AND THINK

Review the following set of objectives using the questions below:

- ◆ Does the set contain an appropriate representation of cognitive behaviours?
 - ◆ Does the set contain an adequate representation of affective behaviours?
 - ◆ Is the set of objectives broad enough to cover the subject adequately?
 - ◆ Are all the objectives internally consistent?
1. To develop the competence to understand oral texts in varied communicative situations showing a respectful and positive attitude towards the conversational process.
 2. To autonomously produce oral messages appropriate to the situation and the communicative intention, using basic communicative strategies, linguistic and non-linguistic for the communication process to be fluent and accurate.
 3. To acquire the competence to use English in real- life situations for the development and maintenance of interpersonal relationships and to take part in interpersonal encounters through the sharing of factual and attitudinal information; valuing and respecting other's opinion.
 4. To value and use errors as a part of the process of learning.
 5. To understand written texts with different purposes, assessing its importance as a source of information, enjoyment and leisure and as a way of accessing to cultures and ways of life different to ours.
 6. To show interest in improving reading skills, developing the capacity to value literary texts.
 7. To read autonomously to obtain global and specific information from texts adequate to the capacities and interests of the students developing and using learning strategies.
 8. To write simple and brief texts useful for daily life using connectors, grammar and appropriate lexis following a written model and free writing.
 9. To reflect upon the foreign language system and its components (morphology, phonology and syntax) valuing the importance of accuracy and fluency in communication.
 10. To transfer learning strategies learnt in other languages to the learning of English in order to carry out tasks.
 11. To reflect about the process of learning and about the degree of achievement of the objectives proposed, as well as about the way to improve one's processes of learning.
 12. To foster the development of critical thinking skills and the development of learning skills so that students can continue their education beyond the school setting.
 13. To know and value the development of new technologies and to make use of them as a complementary tool in the process of learning in order to favour the use of learning strategies to get, select and present information orally and in writing.
 14. To appreciate the foreign language as a tool for learning and to value the advantages it offers for the acquisition of new knowledge considering it as a becoming element of social and interpersonal relationships.
 15. To value the foreign languages and languages as a mean to establish social relationships and to compare the cultural and social aspects of the English speaking countries with our

own ones, appreciating the natural, cultural, linguistic and historic differences and similarities.

Skilbeck (1984) makes several points about objectives:

- 1 Objectives in a curriculum should be stated as desirable student learning and as actions to be undertaken by teachers to affect, influence or bring about learning. It is important that they are clear, concise. They should also be understood by the learners themselves.
- 2 Objectives are directional and dynamic in that they must be re-examined, modified and if necessary reformulated as the teaching-learning process unfolds.
- 3 Objectives gain their legitimacy by being related systematically both to general aims and to the reality of teaching and learning. They should also have a rational and legitimate basis.

Another distinction which needs to be observed is between objectives which describe what learners will be able to do as a result of instruction (product objectives) and those which describe activities designed to develop the skills needed to carry out the product objectives (process objectives). Product, or, as they are more usually called, performance objectives may refer to grammatical, functional, thematic, or topical skills and knowledge. Process objectives differ from product objectives in that they specify the experiences that the learner will undergo in the classroom.

Objectives can be useful, not only to guide the selection of structures, functions, notions, tasks, and so on, but also to provide a sharper focus for teachers, to give learners a clear idea of what they can expect from a language programme, to help in developing means of assessment and evaluation, and so on.

Grittner (1977) rejects the notion of a goal-directed language curriculum with a quotation from Peters, the English educational philosopher, who writes:

"Education...can have no ends beyond itself. Its value derives from principles and standards implicit in it. To be educated is not to have arrived at a destination; it is to travel with a different view." (Peters, 1965:110)

The critics saw a danger, above all, in the demand for a narrow specificity of performance objectives. In Grittner's view, this would lead to the trivialization of the curriculum and an over-emphasis upon what is measurable, quantifiable, and examinable, and would be nothing more than a modern version of the "coercive use of performance standards" in traditional examination systems. He concludes:

In short, behavioural objectives seem to be part of a system for doing more efficiently that which we should not be doing at all, that is, perhaps we should not be imposing pre-made decisions upon students; perhaps instead we should be

helping them to make their own decisions; to learn how to learn for themselves" (Grittner, 1977:60)

3.2 Syllabus

Now we turn our attention to the selection and sequencing of language content. We understand by syllabus the selection and organization of language content, According to Breen (1987a), a syllabus is a plan that typically maps out a body of knowledge (foreign language) and those capabilities which are regarded as worthwhile outcomes from the work of teachers and learners. In most cases, the plan (syllabus) specifies and selects specific aspects of the foreign language and/or its use in various social situations for a variety of personal and social purposes. According to Breen (1987a; 1987b), every syllabus is a particular representation of knowledge and capabilities. And this representation will be shaped by:

- how the designer views the nature of language,
- how the language may be most appropriately taught or presented to learners, and
- how the language may be productively worked upon during learning.

Syllabi have been classified into propositional plans and process plans by (Breen, 1987a; 1987b) and into analytic and synthetic syllabi by Wilkins (1976). A synthetic approach to syllabus design is that in which the different parts of language are taught separately and step by step. This way the task of the learner consists in a process of gradual accumulation of parts until the structure of language has been completed. A synthetic syllabus is typically associated with a product curriculum.

In contrast, analytic syllabi are organised in terms of the purposes for which a learner is learning the FL and the kinds of language performance that are necessary to meet those purposes (Wilkins, 1976). The starting point of an analytic syllabus is the communicative purposes for which the language is used. Therefore, language is not graded according to grammatical difficulty.

Breen (1987a; 1987b) propositional plans comprise formal syllabuses and functional syllabuses, whereas process plans are divided into task-based syllabi and process syllabi. Breen (1987a; 1987b) describes and compares each type of syllabus with reference to five questions:

- (a) What knowledge does it focus upon and prioritise?
- (b) What capabilities does it focus upon and prioritise?
- (c) On what basis does it select and subdivide what is to be learned?
- (d) How does it sequence what is to be learned?
- (e) What is its rationale?

3.2.1 Propositional plans

For reasons of time and space, in this chapter we are only going to present the characteristics of the main syllabus types in table format.

The formal syllabus consists of a list of grammatical structures. This syllabus is usually divided into different parts graded according to difficulty and/or frequency of usage.

The formal syllabus	
1. What knowledge does it focus on?	<p>A systematic and rule-based view of the nature of language itself.</p> <p>A description and analysis of language.</p> <p>The systematic nature of language itself.</p> <p>Prioritises how a text is realised and organised.</p> <p>A primary concern with a language learner's knowledge of the code of a new language.</p> <p>Subsystems of phonology, grammar, lexis (morphology) and discourse as text are prioritised.</p>
2. What capabilities does it focus on and prioritise?	<p>Language use and skills use, typically proposing that the skills be worked upon in a sequence from the receptive to the productive.</p> <p>It also places emphasis on correctness and accuracy in language production.</p>
3. On what basis does it select and subdivide what is to be learned?	<p>It tries to reflect the organisation or "logic" inherent in the language itself.</p> <p>Typically it identifies pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, morphology, and the structural features of discourse.</p> <p>Criteria for the selection of language items approximate very closely to the analysis undertaken by the linguist.</p> <p>Those aspects of each sub-system which are taken to be appropriate to the 'level' of the learners.</p> <p>The criterion of 'level' is derived from the extent to which a learner has mastered - in terms of accurate production - these linguistic sub-systems.</p>
4. How does it sequence what is to be learned?	<p>Linguistic complexity.</p> <p>Developmental route from simple structures to complex ones.</p> <p>Frequency of usage, and usefulness of structures and vocabulary.</p>
5. What is its rationale?	<p>Four main arguments:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. It is well established and is informed by a long tradition of linguistic analysis. It captures a view of language which many teachers find familiar.

2. It presents learners with a subject-matter which is systematic and rule-governed. The Formal syllabus has the potential to provide the learner with generative knowledge.
3. Because the linguistic system is analysable in terms of propositions, the new language is more amenable to planning as subject matter
4. Such a syllabus calls upon the human capacity to be metalinguistic, to reflect upon, talk about, and try to work out just how a language works.

Functional syllabus

Since the mid-'70s, the Functional syllabus has probably been the alternative to Formal ones which has received the most attention. The Functional syllabus is a propositional plan of language knowledge and capabilities based upon a distinctive view of the nature of content for language pedagogy (Breen, 1987). Functions are the purposes for which we use language. Examples of functions are 'describing', 'narrating', 'greeting'. This type of syllabus usually incorporates notions, too. Notions are the concepts that can be expressed through language ('time', 'distance', 'place', 'quantity'...

<i>Functional syllabus</i>	
1. What knowledge does it focus on?	<p>Sociolinguistics and Pragmatics. These study the relationship between the language code and how people behave in certain situations.</p> <p>Knowledge of how to use language in appropriate ways in order to achieve particular purposes.</p> <p>Speech Act theory</p> <p>The F/N prioritises the purposes which a language can serve and how they are coded through the language.</p>
2. What capabilities does it focus on and prioritise?	<p>Learners will not only become accurate in using the language, but will also learn how to be socially appropriate.</p> <p>Proficiency is identified with the accurate and appropriate use of the four skills.</p> <p>A skill-oriented view of learner capabilities (as in the formal syllabus)</p>
3. On what basis does it select and subdivide what is to be learned?	<p>Types of purposes are identified in sets and subsets... and it further specifies how these functions may be realised in various ways through the language code.</p> <p>How these functions may be realised in various ways.</p> <p>It tries to reflect the organisation or "logic" inherent in the</p>

	<p>language itself. Pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, morphology, and the structural features of discourse. Similar principles of selection and subdivision to those of a comprehensive phrase book.</p>
<p>4. How does it sequence what is to be learned?</p>	<p>From general sets of functions to more specific functions. From most common linguistic realisations of certain functions to more varied or “refined” realisations of these functions. Sequencing is from the general to the particular or, more precisely, cyclic in nature</p>
<p>5. What is its rationale?</p>	<p>The F/N S is an expression of a sociolinguistic view of the purposes language can achieve. It aims at enabling learners to use language - virtually from the outset of their learning - in order to achieve things in an interpersonal or social way Fluency is valued as much as linguistic accuracy. Concern for meaningfulness as an important element in the language learning experience.</p>

The functional syllabus is criticized on the following grounds:

- The selection and grading of items become much more complex than in the formal syllabus.
- Situational, contextual, and extra-linguistic factors tend to complicate the issues of simplicity and difficulty.
- Inventories of functions and notions do not necessarily reflect the way languages are learned.

STOP AND THINK

Read the following quote and comment on its implications for syllabus design

...a person does not learn by receiving ‘input’ that is ‘delivered’ via some instructional mechanism, but by picking up information in the environment on the basis of and guided by organismic needs and purposes. The latter is a very different perspective on learning, and one that changes the pedagogical ballgame completely. The curriculum does not start out by specifying and sequencing the material that is to be ‘covered’, but it starts out with the activities, needs and emergent purposes of the learner. (van Lier, 2007: 53)

Process plans

Process plans represent how something is done. According to Breen (1987a) they will seek to represent knowledge in terms of *how*:

- correctness,

- appropriacy, and
- meaningfulness can be simultaneously achieved.

Task-based syllabus	
1. What knowledge does it focus on?	<p>Communicative competence as a unity of text, interpersonal behaviour, and ideation.</p> <p>The learner's experience and awareness of language learning.</p>
2. What capabilities does it focus on and prioritise?	<p>Communicative competence and learning how to learn.</p> <p>The ability to negotiate meaning, the ability to interpret meaning, the ability to express meaning</p>
3. On what basis does it select and subdivide what is to be learned?	<p>Analysis of the actual tasks which a person may undertake when communicating through the target language.</p> <p>Learning tasks: selected on the basis of metacommunicative criteria. They provide the groundwork for the learner's engagement in communication tasks and deal with learner difficulties which emerge during these tasks, addressing i) how the knowledge systems work, and ii) how the learning may be best done.</p> <p>Subdivision is on the basis of task types (various ways).</p>
4. How does it sequence what is to be learned?	<p>Sequencing "can ... be characterised as cyclic in relation to how learners move through tasks, and problem-based (or problem-generated) in relation to the on-going difficulties which learners themselves discover.</p> <p>The criteria for sequencing are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the relative familiarity of the task to the learner's current communicative knowledge and abilities, and • the relative inherent complexity of the task in terms of the demands placed upon a learner. <p>Sequencing in the task-based syllabus depends upon:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a) the identification of learning problems or difficulties as they arise; b) the prioritising of particular problems and the order in which they may be dealt with; c) the identification of appropriate learning tasks which address the problem areas.
5. What is its rationale?	<p>Broader view of what is to be achieved in language learning.</p> <p>Insights from SLA research:</p>

1. has no effect on developmental sequences,
2. has a positive effect on the use of some learning strategies,
3. clearly improves rate of learning, and,
4. probably improves the ultimate level of SL attainment.

The learner's initial competence can be engaged as the foundation upon which new knowledge and capabilities may be accommodated during the undertaking of tasks, matching the process which occurs when learners mobilise knowledge systems when undertaking actual tasks in the L1.

Participation in communication tasks which require the learners to mobilise and orchestrate knowledge and abilities in a direct way will itself be a catalyst for language learning.

A more sensitive methodology: represents the effort to relate content to how that content may be worked upon, and thereby, learned more efficiently.

Means-focused and ends-focused.

Assumes that learning is necessarily both metacommunicative and communicative.

Based on the belief that learners can be analytical in their exploration of communication in the target language and of the knowledge and ability use it entails.

"... rests on the principle that metacommunicating is itself a powerful springboard for language learning.

A process syllabus, in contrast to the previous types, is the only one which does not predetermine language content. Course content is usually negotiated with the learners during the year (Candlin, 1984; Legutke and Thomas, 1991). The process syllabus is a plan for classroom work. This plan/framework enables teacher and learners to do these things themselves

From product to process

Take a particular ESO year that you want or need to plan.

First, try planning it according to the seven stages suggested by Taba.

➡ *Diagnose needs*

■ *what is the problem that you want to address?*

➡ *Set objectives*

- *what is it you want to achieve.* Remember an objective involves a clear statement of the change to be achieved, and a timescale for its completion.
- *select content* - what areas do you want to cover.
- *organize content* - is there a good order to tackle things in? Here it is important to think of the learners' experience. What is the best way of tackling things so that they may learn?
- *selection of learning experiences* - what activities, exercises, inputs are needed?
- *organize learning experiences* - looking at the content, your objectives and the activities you want to use, is there a sound order? Is there anything you need to book, plan or set up?
- *agree and organize evaluation* - how are you going to make judgements about outcomes?

Second, approach it as a process. This involves thinking about:

- ➡ *Aim.* Remember here that aims are broader than objectives - they concern the purpose or direction of the work rather than specific changes to be achieved.
- ➡ *Planning principles.* This involves looking at many of the things we have already listed above - how content is to be selected; how is learning to be facilitated; and what order should things be taken in. However, rather than focus on outcome, think about process. How may you help to create environments that foster conversation and that connect with the aim?
- ➡ *Principles concerning process and evaluation.* How is participants' progress to be assessed; how is our development as educators to be evaluated; how are we to make judgements about process?

3.3 Methodology

Richards, Platt and Weber (1985:117) define methodology as *the study of the practices and procedures used in teaching, and the principles and beliefs that underlie them*. In turn, Richards and Rodgers (1982, 1986), adopting a three part analysis proposed by Anthony (1963), set up a useful framework for the systematic description of methods. They define method in terms of three levels: *approach*, *design*, and *procedure*. By *approach*, they mean a theory of language and of language learning, by *design* they mean the definition of linguistic content and a specification for the selection

and organization of content and a description of the role of the teacher, learner and teaching materials, while by *procedure* they mean the description of techniques and practices in the instructional system.

Methodology in language teaching has been characterized in a variety of ways. A more or less classical formulation suggests that methodology is that which links theory and practice. In this sense, theory statements would include theories of what language is and how language is learned or, more specifically, theories of second language acquisition (SLA). Such theories are linked to various design features of language teaching. These design features might include stated objectives, syllabus specifications, types of activities, roles of teachers, learners, materials, and so forth. Design features in turn are linked to actual teaching and learning practices as observed in the environments where language teaching and learning take place. This whole complex of elements defines language teaching methodology. This view is summarised in the figure below:

The 'method' variable, then, plays a very important role in determining what goes on in the classroom. What actually happens in the classroom (excluding for the moment the contribution of the learners themselves) is thus an interaction of the teaching method which is officially being used and the individual teacher's interpretation of this method.

In planning the curriculum teachers are expected to minimally:

- specify the principles underlying classroom intervention
- select learning experiences - what activities, exercises, inputs are needed?
- organize learning experiences - looking at the content, your objectives and the activities you want to use, is there a sound order? Is there anything you need to book, plan or set up?
- decide on seating arrangements
- determine learner and teacher roles.

3.4 Evaluation

Evaluation is usually the last component in curriculum design. It is true that evaluation

often occurs at the final stage in the curriculum process. However, we support a view of evaluation that runs parallel with other curriculum activities and may occur at different times during the planning and implementation phases, as well as during a specified evaluation phase. The term evaluation has frequently been taken to indicate the assessment of students at the end of the course, but more recently its meaning has been extended to include all aspects of a programme. Skilbeck (1984:238) has made a useful distinction between assessment and evaluation:

...assessment in the curriculum is a process of determining and passing judgements on students' learning potential and performance; evaluation means assembling evidence on and making judgements about the curriculum including the processes of planning, designing, and implementing it.

The primary purpose of assessment is to determine whether or not the objectives of a course of instruction have been achieved. Assessment is the process of observing, recording and otherwise documenting the work learners do and how they do it, as a basis for a variety of educational decisions that affect the learner, including planning for groups and individual learners. Assessment encompasses the many forms of evaluation available to educational decision makers. Assessment in the service of curriculum and learning requires teachers to observe and analyze regularly what the learners are doing in light of the content goals and the learning processes. Questions relating to evaluation in curriculum planning include the following:

- Who is to evaluate?

Traditionally this has been the role of the teacher. Nowadays, when this question is asked a number of candidates emerge. Obviously, teachers, and, in a learner-centred curriculum, the learners themselves will certainly be involved. Other participants may include outside experts, observers or interested parties. Teachers may wish occasionally to involve their colleagues in peer observation of lessons, or part of lessons.

- How are the teacher and the students going to evaluate?

There are a variety of tools and techniques that a teacher can use. They may include standardised tests of various sorts, along with questionnaires, observation schedules of classroom interaction, interview schedules, learner diaries and so on. The most important thing is that the tool selected should be appropriate to the task.

- What is going to be evaluated?

The specific method of evaluation will relate to what exactly a teacher or would like to assess. The specific choice of focus and range will depend on the age and level of the students, the nature of curriculum and language content. Any element in the curriculum process may be evaluated, as any may affect learner progress, and it is up to teachers to decide. Evaluation as a decision making in the classroom is not only about student achievement, it is also about the processes and factors that affect student achievement. Some of the aspects that can be evaluated are planning procedures, goals

and objectives, the selection and grading of content, materials and learning activities, teacher performance and the assessment processes themselves. Obviously, the most obvious candidate for evaluation is student achievement. A teachers needs to know what and how much students have learnt in order to monitor the effectiveness of teaching, to make changes in teaching, and for accountability purposes.

STOP AND THINK

Read the questions below and think of how and when you would use them.

- ◆ Did my student evaluation plan permit me to probe sufficiently into my students' knowledge, understanding, skills, attitudes, and processes?
 - ◆ Did I consider the appropriateness of my assessment techniques in conjunction with the instructional approaches used?
 - ◆ Were my assessment techniques appropriate for the student information required?
 - ◆ Did my assessment techniques allow my students to show their best performance?
 - ◆ Were my assessment techniques fair and appropriate for the levels of my students' abilities?
 - ◆ Did the range of information I collected allow me to make interpretations and evaluate my students' progress?
 - ◆ Did my student evaluation plan allow me to report results meaningfully to my students, their parents, and other educators?
- When will evaluation take place?

In evaluation theory, theorists distinguish between summative and formative evaluation. The first refers to summative assessment at the end of the course. The second is formative assessment which takes place as the course proceeds. Ideally, evaluation should be planned from the beginning, a schedule set, participants decided upon, and criteria and procedures agreed by all involved. In fact, evaluation can even begin prior to the start of teaching with a comparison of instructional objectives and incoming students' needs, goals, previous learning experiences, and present levels of language proficiency. There is no doubt that systematic and routine assessment of classroom practice and student achievement during the course can improve day-to-day teaching and learning. It is a major challenge for a busy teacher to evaluate from the beginning to the end of a course, but this is crucial to successful teaching and effective learning.

Although the answers to the questions above are to some extent a matter of personal choice, Genesee and Upshur (1996: 50) offer the following suggestions for evaluation planning:

1. Determine students' needs and abilities at the beginning of the academic year as a basis for assessing the suitability of teaching objectives and for planning instruction.
2. Examine student attainment of lesson and unit objectives on a regular basis.

3. Provide frequent and regular occasions for informing students about learning success.
4. Monitor classroom activities on a regular basis in order to ascertain their effectiveness.
5. Examine student attainment of general instructional objectives.

To summarise this section, an evaluation plan should include the following:

- A list of evaluation criteria, specifying what is going to be evaluated.
- A description of assessment techniques.
- A schedule of when to carry out the assessment activities needed to provide the preceding information.
- A description of the record-keeping systems to be used.

STOP AND THINK

Read the following and write a brief reflection on the paradox.

The more teachers take over responsibility for and control over the language behaviour of learners, the more it diminishes the autonomy and independence of the individual. Teacher planning, by necessity, makes schools the ultimate authority of what language learning is, with the power to determine what is learned and how the resulting rewards shall be distributed...

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